

spikelet sterility. In the BC₅ also, pollen and spikelet sterility were maintained in the progenies. The CMS line derived from progeny 1 was named Pusa 5A.

The outcrossing potential of this line was evaluated against IR58025 A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10A using the respective B lines. Pusa 5A recorded a seed yield of 2.8 t ha⁻¹ vs 2.0, 0.6, 0.7, and 0.8 t ha⁻¹ of IR58025A, PMS2A, PMS3A, and PMS10 A, respectively. Pusa 5A had more tillers, longer panicles, more spikelets panicle⁻¹, and better stigma exertion than IR58025A. Pusa 5A may therefore prove to be a good alternative to IR58025A, the most popular cytoplasmic male sterile line used in India. ■

Field evaluation of thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines

C.H.M. Vijayakumar, M.Ilyas-Ahmed, B.C. Viraktamath, M.S. Ramesha, and S. Singh, Directorate of Rice Research, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

The use of thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) is well recognized in two-line heterosis breeding. The use of the TGMS system has several advantages over the cytoplasmic genic male sterility system, such as (1) its simple and efficient seed production system, and (2) its greater scope for enhancing heterosis because any genotype can be used as a male parent. To develop hybrids using the TGMS system, it is necessary to identify or develop lines that show a desirable transformation from fertility to sterility and vice versa.

We evaluated several TGMS lines that carried TGMS genes introduced from IRRI. Besides intensive study under field conditions for five seasons, starting in 1994, we made simultaneous individual plant selections in these lines. The TGMS lines were (1) IR68945-4-33-14, (2) IR68948-12-3-7, (3) IR68949-11-5-31, (4) IR68945-4-33-4-14, and (5) IR32364-120-1-3-2. Lines 1, 2, and 3 showed very good transformation between seasons. At Hyderabad,

during the wet season, the weather is unstable and daily mean temperatures below 25 °C occur frequently. The daily maximum temperature is 29 °C, which induces fertility in most of the IRRI-bred TGMS lines. During the dry season, however, the daily mean temperature is always >25 °C, with a daily maximum of >32 °C beginning in the second week of March, which induces sterility in most lines, including the selected lines 1, 2, 3, and 4.

During the 1995-96 dry season, 325 plant progenies of TGMS lines 1, 2, 3, and 4 were evaluated in two sets planted at 10-d intervals. The results showed that IR68945-4-33-14 still segregated for plant type, grain type, and sterility, whereas IR68948-12-3-7 and IR68949-11-5-31 were almost stable. Another line, IR68945-4-33-4-14, was uniform, but partially fertile, and appeared to be a very high-temperature sterile type. Plants showing stable sterility were selected and their stubble was planted in the 1996 wet season, in which all those lines transformed to fertility further confirmed their behavior. IR32364-120-1-3-2 did not set seeds in either season after 1994. Although the anthers were light yellow, they did not shed any pollen, which was >99% abortive type. Perhaps it is a very low-temperature fertile type. Lines IR68948-12-3-7 and IR68949-11-5-31, which also have desirable floral traits that influence outcrossing, will be used in hybrid rice breeding in the coming years. ■

Developing thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines in rice

K. Thiyagarajan, P. Jayamani, R. Latha, P. Suthamathi, and M. Rangaswamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

The three-line method (A/B/R) of heterosis breeding is cumbersome and warrants development of alternate approaches to exploit hybrid vigor commercially in rice. Two-line breeding

is one such possibility that emerged following the chance discovery of photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines and thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines in China.

A study was conducted to identify a stable TGMS source from suspected and introduced TGMS lines under natural conditions. Thirty-eight lines were evaluated at Coimbatore (high temperature 38/23 °C) and at Gudalur (low temperature 30/16 °C) simultaneously during summer 1995. Pollen fertility in these lines was recorded during the flowering stage using I-KI (1%) solution. Panicles were bagged and spikelet fertility recorded.

Lines TS 15 and TS 16 showed 100% pollen sterility at Coimbatore and 55-80% pollen fertility at Gudalur. The sterile lines are maintained as stubble at Coimbatore for further evaluation in the wet season. These lines are also evaluated under controlled conditions to determine the critical sterility and fertility points of temperature. Crosses are also made simultaneously with agronomically superior lines to transfer the TGMS genes. ■

Male sterility and fertility behavior of suspected thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines

C.R. Elsy and M. Rangaswamy, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

The male sterility-fertility response in thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was studied to identify their adaptability to different temperature regimes. Twenty suspected TGMS lines available at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, were used for the study. The plants of these lines, which were completely male sterile during summer 1995, were tagged and observed for their male sterility-fertility behavior in the ratooned tillers during winter 1995 and summer 1996 by staining pollen grains with I-KI. Panicle development stages, from the

formation of pollen mother cells to the late uninucleate stage of pollen grains, were considered as sensitive to temperature. These stages occurred 9-19 d prior to heading (or 9-17 d after panicle initiation). Therefore, the critical temperature at which plants showed variation in pollen sterility and fertility was calculated by considering the average daily temperature and average maximum temperature prevalent during 9-19 d prior to heading.

Observations on the mean daily and maximum temperature during the sensitive stages of the identified TGMS lines indicated that these lines showed more pollen fertility when the mean daily temperature was $\leq 26^\circ\text{C}$, with a mean maximum temperature of $< 32^\circ\text{C}$. Similarly, a majority of the lines became male sterile when the mean temperature was $> 27^\circ\text{C}$, with a mean maximum temperature of $> 33^\circ\text{C}$. TGMS 6 (RP2161-106-1 S), TGMS 9 (mutant of IR50), TGMS 10 (C12 japonica purple S), TGMS 16 (IR68945-33-4-14-40 S), and TGMS 18 (IR68949 S) showed sterility-fertility changes under such temperature conditions. These lines showed high pollen fertility in December and January and pollen sterility in April and May. TGMS 16 and TGMS 18 remained pollen-free with empty anther sacs in the peak summer months, indicating the more stable nature of these lines. TGMS 18 remained pollen-free up to the first fortnight of June.

In November, TGMS 6 showed 25% pollen fertility at a mean daily temperature of 27°C and mean maximum of 31°C . When the mean daily temperature remained the same during March, but the mean maximum rose to 35°C , it showed 100% pollen sterility. This indicated the pronounced influence of maximum temperature on the sterility-fertility behavior of this line. For TGMS 18 also, the influence of maximum temperature became clearer, when the line showed 80% pollen fertility during September at a mean daily temperature of 27°C and maximum temperature of 32°C . The line turned out to be 100%

sterile when plants were exposed to the same mean daily temperature (27°C), but a higher maximum temperature (34°C).

These TGMS lines can be successfully used in two-line breeding by undertaking hybrid seed production programs in areas where constantly high temperatures (mean daily temperature $> 27^\circ\text{C}$, mean maximum temperature $> 33^\circ\text{C}$) prevail in the summer months. Similarly, these lines can be maintained at high-altitude areas where the temperature is low or even in the plains during December-January. ■

Hybrid rice research in Pakistan

Syed Sultan Ali and M.G. Khan, Rice Research Institute, Kala Shah Kaku, Pakistan

In Pakistan, hybrid rice research began in 1991-92. In evaluations made during 1992-95, IRRI hybrids outyielded local varieties KS 282 and IR6 by more than 50%. For practical exploitation of hybrid rice technology, local Basmati and non-Basmati germplasm is being converted into commercially usable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines. 17156A is the newly developed Basmati CMS line (male sterility source, IR58025A). Restorers are being identified for this line. Less restorer and higher maintainer frequency were observed in local germplasm. Therefore, $A \times R$ and $R \times R$ crosses are being made to increase restorer frequency. Maintainer frequency is being increased using $B \times B$ crosses. IR58025A, IR62829A, IR68897A, IR68896A, IR69617A, and 913A showed an excellent stigma exertion ratio, outcrossing rate, and other floral characteristics that influence outcrossing. One recessive gene for aroma and two dominant genes for fertility restoration of wild abortive cytoplasm were observed. Anther length and pollen grain size were observed to be monogenically controlled traits. Thermosensitive genic male sterility and the wide compatibility trait are being studied. Recently

developed hybrid IR58025A / KS 282 is being field-tested. Target areas for seed production are being located. Grain quality analysis shows that both parents should have acceptable grain quality to develop rice hybrids possessing that same quality. ■

Hybrid rice: status and future in Bangladesh

A.W. Julfikar, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur-1701, Bangladesh

The Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) started hybrid rice research in 1993 through an informal collaboration with the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). Initial work involved testing F_1 hybrids, and evaluating cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) and restorer lines received from IRRI. In CMS lines IR58025A and IR62829A, an outcrossing rate of 3% was recorded. The maintainers showed 80-90% spikelet fertility and a number of restorers were also identified. Some well-adapted varieties / lines were identified as maintainers or good restorers for the wild abortive cyto-sterility system. Some elite restorer lines are BR29, BR5876-6-2-1, BR4839-17-2-2-HR42, BR5690-62-23, BR5882-12-2-1 and BR5892-32-5-3. Some Chinese CMS lines and their maintainers were also evaluated for their adaptability and performance. These Chinese lines were not adapted to Bangladesh conditions and were highly susceptible to disease and insects.

A number of IRRI-developed hybrids were tested in multilocal yield trials during the 1995-96 boro season at Gazipur, Comilla, Bhanga, and Habiganj. A number of rice hybrids outyielded the standard check variety of the same duration by more than 1 t ha^{-1} . Grain quality characteristics of the tested hybrids were comparable with those of our recommended check varieties. These results have encouraged rice scientists and policymakers to develop and use hybrid rice technology in Bangladesh.